

MAPPING IN THE EMERGENCY: DESIGNING A HYPERLOCAL AND SOCIALLY CONSCIOUS SONIFIED MAP OF COVID-19 IN SUFFOLK COUNTY, NEW YORK

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we describe a hyperlocal ArcGIS- and sonification-based COVID-19 web-mapping tool that seeks to ameliorate some of socio-technical problems associated with epidemiological mapping and the field's frequent usage of visual and haptic data display. This socio-technical problems can be seen in current, well-known and frequently cited epidemiological mapping tools, such as the Johns Hopkins University COVID-19 Dashboard, which face functional and formal design challenges when compared to the hyper-phenomenal scope of the ongoing pandemic. As a review of our current project scope, we describe the stakes of the pandemic and pose questions related to the aforementioned design challenges that tools deploying data display may face. Taken as a whole, our project aims to offer a response to some of these design challenges by offering user choice and control, n-dimensional data display via sonification, and the integration so socio-political data into epidemiological layers to better represent Suffolk County's lived experience with COVID-19

1. INTRODUCTION: STAKES

The Covid-19 Pandemic as a totality pervades epidemiological and health policy responses as well as the healthcare systems tasked with implementing them. Its consequences and reactions to it also reveal a plethora of substrata that represent the environmental, social, technical, cultural, and political geographies of our society. This complex harkens the pandemic as being a true hyperobject—object that has been so popularized by Timothy Morton. [1] That the size, scope, and complexity of the pandemic would hold the characteristics of a hyperobject, should come as no surprise: the pandemic “sticks” to all of us, as we keep our distance from one another, wear masks, some of us become ill, or even worse, die; the consequences and “dimensional phase space” of the pandemic may manifest themselves in local ways, yet are determinedly non-local as the pandemic is global in scale, and its wide ranging effects are often invisible in myriad ways like

the case of “long COVID,” where suffering persists after the most acute symptoms have subsided [1, p. 1]. As with all pandemics before COVID-19, its effects will careen across bodies and time, and more specifically, as COVID-19 becomes endemic, the consequences for public health will play out over the coming decades. Part of understanding the pandemic's scope has been a turn toward data visualization, sonification, and mapping tools to make sense of the epidemiology. These tools may also be thought of as aiming to reveal the pandemic as hyperobject through the “interrelationships between [the] aesthetic properties of objects”—i.e., wave shaped disease incidence and mortality graphics, images of COVID-19 triage wards, casual photos of people with masks worn around the wrist outdoors, and so on—collide, assembling a graphic simulacrum of the pandemic's meaning [1, p. 1]. The interrelationships between aesthetically rendered objects require rethinking the design of the widespread pandemic data display tools.

The production of health-data spurred on by the Affordable Care and Patient Protection Act, has allowed for longitudinal cultural, institutional, economic, and political documentation of the pandemic in the United States [2, 3]. One popular form of data visualization in the US has been data mapping, such as web-tools like the New York Times Coronavirus tracking map [4], and its subsequent interactive media that mark COVID-19 death milestones [5, 6], or from academia the Johns Hopkins University Coronavirus Resource Center COVID-19 Map [7]. While both tools are popular and high quality, they put on full display the limitations of current data-mapping paradigms, raising a slew of questions: What is the best way to communicate clearly with the public? How are individuals motivated to cooperate with public health measures such as vaccination, mask-wearing, and social distancing through these tools? How do they engage with or ignore issues of social and economic justice? How will future individuals historicize the pandemic's scale of human suffering after the pandemic ends? How can design choices illuminate unseen relationships for researchers? How do differences in data display and user experience influence embodied understandings of abstract numbers?

Addressing concerns about user comprehension and design re-

quires examining major data presentation methods and researching alternative modes of conveying information incorporating historical data as well as artistic research on aesthetics that can then be mobilized through technological development. It is with these concerns in mind that our small working group at Stony Brook University, comprised of Dr. George Aumoithe, Dr. Margaret Schedel, Litzy Escobar, Inderjeet Bilkhu, and Dr. Eric Lemmon began mapping the lived experience of COVID-19 within a single New York County. We were later joined by Haotong Zhu for additional front-end support. We employ a variety of solutions to the data-mapping design problems laid out in this project review. With the purpose of encouraging a broader conversation on the very tools we use to inform ourselves; this paper will reflect briefly on the state of the field of data mapping from the perspective of historically and theoretically situated problems in data display. It will subsequently describe how our in-progress mapping project addresses these criticisms with our own data-mapping tool.

2. REFLECTING ON DATA MAPPING AND DATA DISPLAY IN THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Most representations of COVID-19-related data for public consumption have come in the form of regularly updated data visualizations and tables. Some of these mapping tools explicitly link factors such as demographic data from race and gender to COVID-19 case incidence, prevalence, and mortality, often using these measures to visualize disparities [8]. Other, more narrative attempts to bring the pandemic into clearer view have focused on the biographies of victims [5]. Some have also attempted to situate the pandemic within the historical record and employ historical precedents ranging from the bubonic plague to the Spanish flu to project the pandemic's future course [9, 10]. Similarly, the pandemic's association with 'waves' has been raised as an issue within its imagery and discourse as it transforms human populations into a passive (non-subjective) medium through which a pandemic propagates [11, 12]. Many of these discussions that look to the past and attempt to humanize statistics with narrative tragedy rightfully seek to contextualize the contemporaneous avalanche of numbers and graphs. Yet, in theoretical circles, such as anthropology, sound studies, and visual studies, these literary and visual forms of representation have faced criticism for narrowing the potentials for sensory understanding and for their eurocentric learning biases [13, 14, 15]. Similar critiques have cropped up in sound studies [16] and have even come from the field of sonification—even as sonification's relationship with visualization is often a partnership rather than antagonistic [17]. These critiques are pointed, in that drawing blueprints from the past or from the hegemonic "visualism" of the west, where visualization is synonymized with understanding, are inadequate for demonstrating COVID-19's scale and impact—especially on historically marginalized populations [13, p.39]. Therefore, modes of representation that incorporate multimedia tools and reinsert human stories into the pandemic's visual and sonic narrative are important. Further, emphasizing customizability and user choice can help users relate to data in ways that connect numerical points with personal meaning.

One solution to the problems associated with visualization from the perspective of accessibility as well as counteracting the aforementioned visualism is to engage with forms of data display and design that mobilize senses beyond sight. Crystal Lee, Alan Lundgard and Arvind Satyanarayan at MIT have recently approached alternatives to visualization design through the mobilization of haptic

and tactile data display technologies [18]. Haptic displays tend to be expensive and unreliable for broad implementation [19, 20], however, and contrast with the relatively cheap deployment of sonification—a technique for auditory data display readily mobilized in web-based applications and implemented using open-source technologies and readily accessible algorithms for development [21, 22, 23].

Sonification is used in fields ranging from artistic production and medical technologies to geological monitoring [24, p.1-2]. Its technological development has grown since the field's founding of the International Community for Auditory Display (ICAD) thirty years ago in 1992 [25]. With broad scale implementation across many disciplines, sonification has held several practical differences versus visual forms of display, due—in part—to our auditory systems allowing for multiple layers of understanding for concurrent sounding objects and being superior at recognizing "temporal changes and patterns" [26, p.11]. Further, by conveying information through sound, sonification tools allow users to examine data without visually attending to them as well (our ears are always 'on' and take in information from the surroundings) [26, p.13].

Other researchers have already used sonification to explore the Covid-19 pandemic from a variety of perspectives. Several have focused on producing sonifications of the molecular structure and genetics of the coronavirus. For example, Enzo De Sena and Milton Mermikides created a longitudinal, multi-modal representation of the Covid-19 genome as it developed over the course of the pandemic [27]. Markus J. Buehler and Ka Hei Cheng have produced sonification tools that allow for the navigation of the spike-protein's structure and genomic data, respectively [28, 29]. Rayam Soeiro et al. have produced a temporally mapped sonification of the initial stages of the pandemic for larger regions of the globe [30]. Debra McGrory, working out of the Urban Systems Lab at The New School developed a series of sonifications that utilized a combination of social impact variables and Covid-19 data from New York City [31]. Web-based and interactive dashboards have explored both COVID-19 and other subjects. Miranda Salazar created an interactive dashboard of soundwalks through a select set of cities to display the changes in the sonic environment via audio decomposition [32]. Mark Temple designed a web-based auditory display tool for the Sonification of DNA base pairs [33]. However, allowing for users to both select the socio-political data point they wish to explore in relation to covid-19 data, as well as map said data point to sounds of their choosing, has not been a fully-fledged feature in these examples.

With these critical concerns in mind, our working group began developing a new COVID-19 mapping tool that would put the dimensionality of the hyper-phenomenal pandemic on display. Our ArcGIS based mapping tool is being built to represent social and cultural data and documentation alongside epidemiological data, allow for sonification as a method of data display, and to allow for user choice in what data is displayed and how it is displayed.

3. INTEGRATED WEBAUDIO AND ARCGIS TO MAP THE LIVED EXPERIENCE OF COVID-19 IN SUFFOLK COUNTY, NY

Starting in June 2021, our group began planning and building out an interactive online and socially conscious map of the lived experience of Covid-19 in Suffolk County. We combined the power of ArcGIS and its relational data management system, and a Web Audio API based sonification tool developed by members of our

team. We were inspired by Stony Brook’s BioMedical Informatics OpenHealth Platform [34] which allows users to choose which database parameters they want to map to display parameters. For example, the number of carcinoma diagnoses could be mapped to visualizations such as size and color. Through a seed grant, our group began integrating these tools and inspirations to enable users to explore the social epidemiology of COVID-19 by choosing their own mapping. In tandem with ESRI’s ArcGIS Maps, our platform is being designed from the outset to trace public reaction to COVID-19 public health responses on public fora such as Twitter and offer presentations of audio-visual data to coincide with the sonification of epidemiological and demographic data. By doing so, our platform is planned to sonically and visually represent everything from measuring the time between initial symptomatic infection and accessing care to trends in decreasing general hospital, and especially intensive care unit (ICU) bed availability. Users can choose which parameters to display, and how they map to the available visual or sonic aspects available. For example ICU bed availability could be mapped to the size of a dot, or the volume of recorded interviews. We don’t anticipate that a user will choose to map every parameter we have collected or linked to; rather users will be able to choose which data is relevant to their own interests, and choose how they wish to display it in both the visual and auditory domains. We think the real strength of our tool is the opportunity to relate existing quantitative data with qualitative historical and cultural data, enhancing understanding of the social determinants of health related to the COVID-19 pandemic.

This project to date has included building the ArcGIS environment with multiple layers of information related to demographics (age, gender, race, household wealth), epidemiology (Covid-19 incidence, prevalence, and mortality), and more novel layers of information (type of housing, property value, profession, region, nearby healthcare facilities, and rates of insurance). We have extrapolated most information from existing U.S. Census, ArcGIS, and disease surveillance datasets. Our team downloaded and modified existing open access Suffolk County data to use in ArcGIS (fig. 1) [35]. For the incorporation of social media data, we have

Figure 1: Example layer with multi-dimensional visual display showing demographic data cross-referenced to Covid-19 cases to date.

drawn upon existing repositories of COVID-19 related tweets [36]. By using the geo-tagged data provided through Twitter’s API, we are able to sort tweets by their geographic location and reference them to specific hamlets, towns, or geographic polygons located within Suffolk County. Using natural language processing techniques such as sentiment and emotion analysis on these texts, we can track the changes of sentiment and emotional valence from social media users tweeting about COVID-19 in Suffolk County over

the course of the pandemic. We are also able to compare this more broadly to global samples with topics related to COVID-19 or the entirety of Twitter’s general discourse. Using the geo-location data attached to these tweets, we are also able to map the average computed values of the textual sentiment via ArcGIS. Furthermore, the data selected for display in the application, whether it be from the built-in ArcGIS layers or new data uploaded by users, can be mapped to discrete sonification parameters. For example, COVID-19 case numbers in the hamlets of Suffolk County at a particular time point could be mapped to the frequency value of a square wave. When the user’s cursor scrolls over the hamlet on the map, the frequency is modulated so that higher case numbers result in a higher pitch, and lower case numbers, a lower pitch. A different parameter, like the number of hospitalizations, could be similarly associated to a sound with a different timbre, like that of a sine tone. Similarly, these data points can be output to different channels. In the case of the standard two-channel output on consumer headphones, this could have the case numbers output to the left, and the hospitalizations to the right. In this way, users would be able to choose the aural representation of the data points they would like to peruse, and the user’s auditory capabilities would be able to track these different data points simultaneously without the need for a visual implementation. The web application is being designed to offer curated selections of these visual and sonic representations that highlight particular narratives our team has found interesting in the course of work. However, we see user-choice as being integral to the aesthetic experience of Covid-19 mapping, as users then have the opportunity to work with the mapping tool in the way that best suits their preferences. The tool also has the added benefit of allowing users with visual disabilities to engage with data display on the pandemic on a granular level that compares with the current suite of extant data visualization tools. To capture some of the qualitative experiences of the Covid-19 pandemic we also plan to gather community data using an English-Spanish survey via snowball sampling. Our draft survey asks about Suffolk County residents’ experiences with the pandemic. It encourages survey respondents to share any images, video, and other audio-visual information with captions. These curated audio-visual documents will provide another layer of on-the-ground data, highlighting individual and familial experiences.

4. CONCLUSIONS: HUMAN EXPERIENCE, DISPLAY DESIGN, AND SOCIO-TECHNICAL ENTANGLEMENTS

At its most basic level, we believe this tool could be a space of qualitative exploration for researchers who are interested in quickly perusing relationships between data sets and identifying them for deeper investigation. In an example from a single timepoint of the pandemic, the authors found that a comparison of demographic data of total Black and white populations in Suffolk County hamlets and their correlated Covid-19 case rates produced sonic results from an early prototype of our web application that have implications for further research.

Link to demo video:

<https://bit.ly/iSon2022MappingTheEmergency>

In the example video above that shows a demonstration of the prototype web application, data for the total population of Black and white residents, as well as their case rates in individual hamlets of Suffolk County have been mapped to simple waveform oscillations

tors that are outputting sound to the left and right audio channels of the user. Black population and case rates are being output to the left channel, while white population and case rates are being output to the right channel. The frequencies of each oscillator are mapped via a linear-to-exponential function. The function takes a domain from 0 to a given maximum value of the aggregate hamlets in Suffolk County to a frequency range of 200 Hz to 2000 Hz (fig. 2).

Figure 2: Screenshot from example of left channel: Black population and Black case rate vs. right channel: white population and white case rate.

For example, the hamlet with the largest white population in the 2017 census tract referenced in the video has 69,209 white residents. Therefore, in the current schema, 0 white residents were mapped to 200 Hz, and 69,209 white residents were mapped to 1000 Hz. Likewise, the hamlet with the largest number of confirmed cases among Black residents was 1,716 at the time-point sampled. Therefore 0 cases among the Black residents of Suffolk County would result in the oscillator returning a frequency of 200 Hz, while 1,716 cases would return 1000 Hz. In this example, when a user is scanning across the map with the cursor, the frequencies of all four data points will adjust according to these values in each hamlet as returned by the mapping function.

With the timepoint sonification selected, the left and right channels become a very rough proportional representation of cases in comparison to population. And when combining this sonification with the geographical boundaries of the map, one can get a sense for the health-policy outcomes according to socio-political and demographic data in individual hamlets. In this particular example, when the pitches on a particular channel are the same or nearly the same (heard through beating interference), one might be able to roughly conclude that the hamlet has tracked near the average case-rate outcome of Suffolk County for the referenced racial group. When the tones of the oscillators are noticeably different, it could highlight an outlier worthy of further investigation.

As part of future design iterations, we hope to make some key improvements to the application. First, simple oscillators can be difficult to differentiate from one another, and psychoperceptual phenomenon such as combination tones, inharmonics, and beating can limit user understanding of the data [37]. Therefore, we are currently working on incorporating options for users to select mappings that include roughness, chroma cycles through harmonic Shepard tones, brightness, and frequency of impulse trains that trigger granular textures [23]. Finally, as much of the COVID-19 data we have received also has a temporal domain with daily data-points (in fact, our twitter data is labeled down to the second), we hope to allow users to ‘play back’ the data from first cases to the present day through a time-series version of the mapping tool.

At its core, this project’s goals are ambitious. We seek to display, through sound and sight, both the macroscopic world of digitized referents alongside the hyperlocal individual experience of a hyperobject that touches us all. At the same time, the user is allowed to decide which combination of data they prefer to compare. The core design challenge in the project is managing the user experience of interacting with the mapping tool’s different visual and aural display types. This is a challenge we gladly confront given the limited suite of existing COVID-19 mapping tools for sonification. A tool that captures the social-political experience of the pandemic is vitally needed.

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